

**OVERVIEW OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING FROM FIKI NAKI:
EFFORTS TO FIND ALTERNATIVE CONCEPTS AND METHODS
FOR ARABIC LEARNING IN THE DIGITAL AGE**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe the concepts and methods of learning foreign languages from Fiki Naki (FN) in the digital age. This research is qualitative descriptive research. The data collection method used in this study is Grounded Theory. Data collection used Library research instruments or Visual Material Review. The research library used eight YouTube videos of interviews with FN and FN's answers to several questions from his fans and used other media sources. The data analysis uses four stages: Codes, Sub-Categories, Categories, and Theory. This study concludes that the FN learning model is suitable for adaptation to foreign language learning to use a foreign language in simple conversation with a native speaker of the target language, not for academic purposes. The concept of learning FN consists of two: psychological and non-psychological. Psychological learning concepts include learning by fun, high determination and consistency, confidence in using Language, and Self-Regulated Learning. The concepts of non-psychological learning include autodidact, intensive learning, direct language practice, imaginary conversation with oneself and practice with native speakers, mastery of vocabulary and phrases with keyword strategies, and effective use of online media. At the same time, the learning method that FN uses is a communicative method with several learning techniques, including a focus on listening and speaking skills, using Mnemonic techniques in vocabulary mastery, and conjugation mastery techniques. The novelty of this research is the description of FN's foreign language learning concepts and methods in self-taught foreign language learning. The researchers recommend analyzing and implementing FN's concepts and learning methods in learning Arabic as a foreign language.

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INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, technology supports foreign language learning. Technology can provide easy and fast access to varied and quality information, materials, and learning resources (Golonka et al., 2014). Technology can also increase interaction and collaboration between students and teachers and between students and native speakers or fellow foreign language learners (Pinto-Llorente, 2020). Technology can also tailor foreign Language learning according to each individual's needs, interests, and learning styles (Zhang & Zou, 2022).

Duolingo, Memrise, Babbel, and Busuu are popular foreign language learning apps. Likewise, YouTube channels offer foreign language learning videos (Alkayisy et al., 2022). This YouTube channel can explain a foreign language's grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, or culture (Anisa et al., 2022). This YouTube channel can also feature dialogues, conversations, or stories in foreign languages that can help improve listening and speaking skills; for example, Fiki Naki's YouTube channel has this link: www.youtube.com/@fikinakiii.

Learning foreign languages in the digital age requires appropriate skills and attitudes from learners. Learners must have digital literacy skills (Afif, 2019), namely the ability to search, evaluate, use, and share information effectively and ethically using technology. Students must also be independent, proactive, critical, and creative in utilizing technology for foreign language learning. Foreign language learning in the digital age also requires active roles from teachers (Azis, 2019). Teachers must be able to design and implement innovative and effective foreign language learning using technology. Teachers must also be able to select and evaluate technology appropriate for the purpose, content, and context of foreign language learning. Teachers must also be able to guide and assist students in using technology for foreign language learning. Foreign Language learning in the digital age offers opportunities and challenges that must be anticipated and utilized by students and teachers (Sari et al., 2022). Learning a foreign language in the digital age can be one way to improve competence and competitiveness in an increasingly connected and diverse global world through a necessary approach called learning autonomy. Christian Ludwig and Maria Giovanna said that the shift to online learning has created space for teachers and students to become more independent, mainly because participating teachers consider autonomy one of the critical capabilities of online learning (Ludwig & Tassinari, 2023).

Learning autonomy is the ability or attitude to take control of one's Learning (Ceylan, 2015). Autonomous learners independently set their learning goals and objectives, choosing materials, tasks, and learning methods that suit their needs and interests (Pinto-Llorente, 2020). Learning autonomy is very important because it can provide benefits such as Increasing student motivation, engagement, and exploration in learning, encouraging learners to play an active role, make decisions, reflect, and evaluate their knowledge, supporting lifelong learning and broader access to education, develop learning skills necessary to adapt to changing times and future challenges.

To develop learning autonomy, learners need appropriate support from teachers, counselors, or other resources to help them identify and use effective learning strategies. Students must also vary in learning to avoid getting bored and stay motivated. Some examples of activities that can improve learning autonomy are Taking notes, flashcards, or example sentences from new vocabulary, Practicing speaking with others who are fluent in a foreign

language or using language learning applications, Reading books, magazines, or articles in a foreign language according to your interests and ability level, Watch movies, videos, or television shows in a foreign language with or without subtitles, Listening to songs, podcasts, or radio in a foreign language and trying to follow lyrics or conversations, Using tools such as Write and Improve to improve writing skills in English.

Students build experience by studying their language, using various sources, including materials, teachers, learning independence, technology, other students, and speakers (2022). Moment here, students no longer depend on the institution to access material and understand language because many materials are available, and the original content and tools make learning Language proficiently with method a worthy and somewhat goal cheap (Betancor Falcon, 2022)

According to Betancor Falcon, structural and material limit innovation and inhibit the development of autonomous learners, thinking critically, and learning lifetime. He believes that rarity and the functional, rational system are the root problems in teaching traditional language. Therefore, there is a need to apply more methodologies aligned with the reality of public information and push the development of students' autonomy, critical thinking, and lifelong Learning (Betancor Falcon, 2022)

Again, according to (Zhang & Zou, 2022) and (Uztosun, 2021), autonomy studies are efficient for researchers to develop learning language independently. In research conducted by Samin, one improvement strategy for the Self-Regulated Learning of Arabic language education students is creating an environment language (Samin & Hikmah, 2021).

However, so that students benefit from using technology to learn an autonomous, appropriate language, support and guidance from the instructor is very important; the teacher plays a vital role as director, mentor, and facilitator in increasing the independence of Study students (Alharbi, 2022). For example, teachers positively support learners by offering choice-relevant information related to the topic and the language spoken, implementing discussion classes and activities in Workgroups, pushing them to evaluate themselves, and stressing the importance of deep LA development (Nguyen et al., 2022). Put forward that advising in learning a language can provide a supportive climate, possible autonomy, and satisfaction needs participant education (Shelton-Strong, 2022). In connection with this, Independence Study He is critical not only as a provider of source Study but especially as a guide for students about How to become independent and access and manage the ocean with Good (Betancor Falcon, 2022). On the other hand, the role of teacher motivation is good, instrumental, and integrative. However, integrative motivation seems more impactful than instrumental (Razem & Pandor, 2023). Technology moment has surpassed dimensions of entertainment and recreation, changing considerable part system activity in various settings, including learning informal language.

Interaction student to learning net- based has been up to the level need principal, even he is future education and very important for offer quality education, implement awareness study emotional in community academic matter this strengthened with lots very research shows online learning (Kerras & Baya Essayahi, 2022) it seems effective among student language England and have in a way significant develop attention students, achievements academics, engagement study student, engagement students, learning active, interaction students, learning process, skills language, skills language English, motivation learn, improve concentrate and deliver experience learn something new as means support study teach as

well as contribute to enhancement interest student (Monika & V, 2022) for control skills communication Arabic, giving chance to learner for develop understanding about various aspect learning language second (Mohamed et al., 2022) this because virtual learning raises aspect positive to Flexibility, learning freedom, and wealth source knowledge (Attiyat et al., 2022).

Contact social own role important in deepening understanding about the use of contextual, semantic lexis, and other aspects of acquisition Language second. Interestingly, social and virtual motivate learners to reach mastery of language. Therefore, there is an urge to use virtual learning about contact social in developing Skills linguistics in acquiring Language second (Attiyat et al., 2022). Study Kissine to receive official Arabic showing that television programs broadcast throughout the Arabic-speaking world constitute source most importantly for children in preschool (Kissine et al., 2019); YouTube was identified as one of the most popular platforms used by teenagers for objective Study (Pires et al., 2022), the mobile digital game produces significant effect to performance Study them and improve acquisition Arabic vocabulary, as well can promote student-centered and interactive learning, while also creating environment learning is as fun as it can be push participation student in activity class, maintain involvement Study them, and improve motivation they (Abdul Ghani et al., 2022)

METHOD

This research is qualitative descriptive research. The data collection method used in this study is *Grounded Theory*. define grounded theory as "a research method concerned with the generation of theory, which is grounded in data that has been systematically collected and analyzed (Ramalho et al., 2015)." Data collection in this study used Observation Instruments or Visual Material Review and Library research. Researchers observed Fiki Naki's videos on his YouTube channel. At the same time, the research library used eight (8) YouTube videos of interviews with Fiki Naki and Fiki Naki's answers to several questions from his fans. The researcher determined these videos through a search engine related to FN's efforts to explore concepts and learning methods in learning a foreign language by autodidact. Apart from video sources, researchers also use other media sources, such as online news media from websites that researchers consider credible websites.

The data analysis uses four stages: Codes, Sub-Categories, Categories, and Theory (Noble & Mitchell, 2016). Purposive participant selection guarantees that a range of linguistic proficiency and cultural origins are represented. In-depth interviews, participant observation, and examination of Fiki Naki's educational materials were used to gather data. Tools such as content analysis, observation checklists, and interview guides are employed to assess the educational materials. Researchers actively participate in Fiki Naki's learning environment as part of the participatory approach, which is the first step in the research process. We conducted in-depth interviews with individuals to get their first-hand knowledge. Direct observation of participants interacting with the learning platform is a component of participatory observation. Thematic analysis was used to examine qualitative data. Essential themes that surfaced from observations and interviews are recognized and examined to get a comprehensive grasp of alternative concepts and approaches in Arabic language learning. The present study conforms to the ethical guidelines for research, which involve securing agreement from participants and authorization from Fiki Naki. Participants' identities are

kept private, and data is safely preserved in compliance with the privacy policy. Data triangulation is used by combining different data sources to ensure validity. Research reliability is maintained through rigor in recording, analyzing data, and interpreting findings.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fiki Naki is a YouTuber from Pekanbaru, Riau. He is famous for his content through channels ometv.com by chatting with foreigners in various languages because he can speak many languages. Fiki Naki (FN) is an online video streamer and Indonesian YouTuber (Fiki Naki - Biodata, Profil, Fakta, Umur, Agama, Pacar, Karier, n.d.). FN became known after uploading content while chatting with foreigners in multiple languages through Ome TV (*Fiki Naki - Wikipedia Bahasa Indonesia, Ensiklopedia Bebas*, n.d.). Some foreign languages he has learned on his own without studying in formal educational institutions or courses. Foreign languages he knows and uses to communicate directly with native speakers include English, Russian, Spanish, French, Romanian, and others. The FN phenomenon appeared publicly after video uploads on YouTube channels, where thousands of people watched and even subscribed to 6.43 million YouTube channels (Akbar & Irianti, 2023). The phenomenon of self-taught foreign language learning through online media gained momentum during the COVID-19 age when all social activities were online. Some videos on the YouTube channel have reviewed some tips on how FN conducts the foreign language learning process self-taught through online media. This study aims to describe the concept and method of learning foreign languages from a phenomenon of FN. The novelty that the researchers display in this study is a scientific analysis of the images and ways of learning FN in learning foreign languages.

Fiki Naki's Learning Concept

Fiki Naki's Learning Concept represents a cutting-edge approach to foreign language acquisition, mainly focusing on the dynamic realm of Arabic language learning in the digital age. Rooted in innovative pedagogy and leveraging modern technologies, Fiki Naki's approach seeks to redefine traditional paradigms of language education. At the core of Fiki Naki's Learning Concept is the seamless integration of technology into the language learning process. The platform harnesses the power of digital tools, interactive applications, and multimedia resources to create an immersive and engaging learning environment. This integration facilitates language comprehension and caters to diverse learning styles. Fiki Naki recognizes the individuality of each learner and tailors the educational experience accordingly. The Learning Concept employs adaptive learning algorithms to assess individual progress and adapt lesson plans to suit the learner's pace and proficiency level. This personalized approach fosters a supportive and effective learning journey. Understanding the cultural nuances of language is integral to Fiki Naki's approach. The Learning Concept goes beyond linguistic elements and incorporates cultural context into the curriculum. Learners acquire language skills and gain insights into the rich cultural tapestry associated with Arabic, enhancing their overall language proficiency.

Fiki Naki's Learning Concept promotes active participation and collaboration among learners. Interactive exercises, real-world scenarios, and collaborative projects are woven into the curriculum, encouraging learners to apply their language skills in practical situations. This approach cultivates a dynamic and engaging learning community. The Learning Concept

places a strong emphasis on continuous assessment and constructive feedback. Regular evaluations, quizzes, and interactive assessments provide learners immediate insights into their progress. The feedback loop is designed to motivate learners and guide them toward areas that require further attention. Fiki Naki's platform extends beyond a mere educational tool; it fosters a supportive community of learners. Forums, discussion groups, and mentorship programs connect learners with peers and educators, creating a collaborative ecosystem of shared knowledge and experiences.

The concept comes from the Latin *Conceptum* or *concept*, which means, in Oxford Learner Dictionaries, "an idea or a principle that is connected with something abstract." As for what learning means, from the views of education and psychology experts, learning is a psycho and physical activity that produces relatively constant changes in knowledge, attitudes, and skills. In this case, what is meant by the concept of learning Fiki Naki is the concept of learning Fiki Naki in learning foreign languages psychologically and physically (Hanafy, 2014).

Psychological Learning Concepts

An interview with FN revealed that FN can make learning foreign languages fun (Learning by fun). Learning something known is essential for desired success, and this was also revealed when many parties tried to explore learning in this foreign language. On another occasion, in an interview. FN revealed that intention and consistency are two things that he cannot separate. Intention without consistency will not produce good results, nor will consistency ever emerge except in the presence of intention and determination. FN's resolution in learning foreign languages can be assessed by spending six hours daily teaching language using the net. The researchers' analysis of existing research sources found that heredity factors may enable FN to communicate with more than one foreign language. It was revealed when interviewed FN that his father could communicate with many regional languages such as Malay, Minang, Acehese, Sundanese, and Javanese. According to Nur Amini dan Naimah, hereditary factors are innate characteristics inherited by biological parents during conception (Amini & Naimah, 2020). Ahmad Badwi said that what influences talent is internal factors, namely personality, and external factors, namely genetic factors (heredity) (Badwi, 2018). Heredity is the first factor in the emergence of skills. It supports individual development in talents as the totality of characteristics inherited by parents to children in all potentials through psychic.

In an interview conducted by FN, they revealed that confidence is essential to language learning success. One of the principles FN built in him was that if we are wrong in expressing language, the target language speakers do not care about it. We do not need to speak perfectly with the accent and intonation of the speakers of the target language; speakers of the target language are already quite happy we speak their language. According to Samin, self-confidence is a significant factor in learning a foreign language, especially learning a foreign language with a communicative approach (Samin et al., 2021).

The concept of learning FN in learning foreign languages is a concept that is needed by anyone who lives in the digital age today (Samin, 2019a). The digital age is an era that requires the idea of Self-Regulated Learning (Samin et al., 2019). One approach to learning in the digital age is the ability of students to build their own learning goals and not solely rely on teachers for the success of their learning process because teachers act like consultants

(Samin et al., 2022). This FN revealed in his interview that he felt he was learning that, at the time, he was learning via the Internet. TN feels that when studying via the net, he finds what he wants, unlike when looking at school conventionally, which he considers monotonous (Samin et al., 2023).

Non- Psychological Learning Concepts

The non-psychological learning concept is FN's learning strategy in learning a foreign language. FN uses an autodidact learning approach. Autodidact comes from two words: Auto, which means alone, and didactic, which means to learn. Autodidact is not easy; FN mentioned in his interview that autodidact requires high consistency. In the web version of the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), autodidact means getting expertise by learning independently. FN conducts the learning of foreign languages online through Youtube.com, ometv.com, and other online media. Efforts to utilize online media in learning are also core in today's digital age and can form self-regulated learning (Samin, 2019b)

Learning a foreign language has other characteristics. FN mentioned in his interview with Sonora.id that one of the quick ways to learn a foreign language is to study intensively because language is a subject that requires a lot of repetition and consistency (Eny et al., 2021), where this is by the theory of language acquisition presented that learning is an active and dynamic process in which individuals utilize various strategic processing methods, apart from that language is a complex cognitive skill that has the same properties as other complex skills in terms of how information is stored and studied. Language learning requires a gradual progression from initial awareness and active manipulation of information and learning processes to automatic language use (Yufrizal, 2023). Learning anything intensively, even if something is liked, someone will still experience boredom. Regarding this saturation, FN moved from one language learning activity to continuing to learn the language despite the changing media. He said that when FN experienced saturation, his learning medium was watching films in the foreign language he was studying. He also said the same thing during an interview with (Elbagiz & Adityo, 2023), and FN explained that when watching a movie, one should not expect to understand many things from the content of the conversation.

In addition to watching movies when he is in a saturated state, FN mentioned in an interview that another thing he does when he is bored is having virtual and offline supportive friends. Regarding communicating with virtual friends, FN has made this medium the primary medium for learning foreign languages. He was learning a foreign language that FN adheres to with a communicative approach, which he uses to communicate with target language speakers through ometv.com media. In addition to ometv.com, which he uses to practice the language he has learned, he also makes this communication medium a means of learning directly with target language speakers. In addition, after talking to native speakers, they will get words with the same meaning but different mentions due to other subjects. The Communicative Method has a theoretical basis, namely the nature and function of language as a means of communication and social interaction (Hermawan, 2018).

Using keywords is one of the stages FN goes through in learning a foreign language. The keywords are "basic words in English, etc." then "basic phrases in English, etc." this strategy of learning with keywords makes it easy for FN to learn words and practices that people often use in daily communication and not be preoccupied with unfamiliar words. After mastering essential words and basic expressions, he watches flogs using subtitles; after

understanding without subtitles, he watches again without subtitles, and then he watches again without subtitles. Moreover, after mastering some videos without subtitles, he moved on to others. After feeling equipped for essential communication with target language speakers, he switched to learning using ometv.com media (Elbagiz & Adityo, 2023). In addition to practicing the target language with native speakers of the target language, he uses imaginary conversations between himself and himself; in other words, he creates communicative conversation questions independently, and he answers these questions alone, both in front of a mirror and while driving FN revealed that the strategy of learning a foreign language did not start from recognizing letters but from knowing the word directly and memorizing it, then practicing the pronunciation by talking to himself. As for learning intonation and eccentricity, he did it through YouTube by watching flogs with the target language.

Fiki Naki's Learning Methods

The method comes from the Greek *Met*, which means to go through or pass, and *hodos*, which means way or way, so the method is the path or way traveled to achieve a specific goal. In the online Cambridge dictionary, it is "a particular way of doing something. (Walmsley, 2016)"

The method is born from an approach (Hermawan, 2018). At the same time, foreign language learning approaches vary with the development of education, psychology, and linguistics research. FN's approach to language learning follows the theory of learning the generative transformation language that Avram Noam Chomsky rolled out in 1959, the result of his critique of the idea of behaviorism that Skinner came up with before. Chomsky held that human behavior was much more complicated than that of animals. Language is closely related to psychology, which consists of the structure of birth (performance), mental structure (performance), and creative aspects of language. Therefore, Chomsky introduced the term "grammar of generative transformation," in this theory, Chomsky said that there is a name Language Acquisition Device (LAD), which is the main factor in the Language (Hermawan, 2018).

In the researcher's analysis of several FN videos on his YouTube channel and with a lot of information from FN related to his learning method, the method he took in learning language was the communicative method. The communicative method is learning a foreign language to use language as a means of communication with speakers of the target language (Hermawan, 2018). This method aims to improve student's language skills in real situations and meaningful social contexts. The communicative way emphasizes functional and interactive language, not just formal mastery of grammar and vocabulary. This method also invites students to actively participate in various language activities, such as conversations, discussions, games, simulations, and others (Hermawan, 2018). FN has made ometv.com the primary medium for using the target language as the language of communication with native speakers of the target language. However, he has never been a native language speaker.

The communicative method began to develop in the 1970s as a reaction to previous methods considered too rigid and mechanical. The communicative approach is based on linguistic, psychological, and pedagogical theories that support natural and enjoyable language learning. Some influential figures in developing communicative methods are

Hymes, Canale, Swain, Widdowson, Krashen, Littlewood, Nunan, and Richards (Hermawan, 2018).

FN has changed from a foreign language learning model to learning a second language without going to the country of native speakers of the target language. He made online media a medium that penetrated geographical, cultural, and psychological boundaries. It is the hallmark of active learners in the Digital age today. The difference between a foreign and a second language is often discussed in applied linguistics, especially in language learning and teaching. The difference between a foreign and a second language is often discussed in applied linguistics, especially in language learning and teaching. Generally, a foreign language is learned by someone not living in a country or region where the language is used for daily communication.

In contrast, a second language is learned by someone who lives in a country or region where the language is used as one of the official or common languages (Prayogi & Shobron, 2020). This difference involves motivation, goals, environment, opportunity, and language difficulty. FN has fulfilled all the conditions for learning a second language by making ometv.com a direct means of communication with native speakers of the target language.

The technique FN uses in learning foreign languages is to focus on two skills more dominantly: listening and speaking; this is because, in the observations of researchers, the purpose of learning FN foreign languages is only limited to being able to communicate with native speakers of the target language, not for academic, political or business purposes. Likewise, the level of language proficiency of the destination is only limited to the ability to converse on the themes that are most commonly the theme of casual chat in friendships. Therefore, when FN was asked in several interviews about his level of foreign language proficiency, he confidently said that he only mastered English with good mastery.

As for some of the techniques that FN uses, one of them is the Mnemonic technique. Mnemonic is a technique of memorizing foreign language vocabulary by associating thoughts, ideas, images, and fantasies. It increases memorization capacity by remembering something new easily and quickly (Putnam, 2015). A Mnemonic is "A mnemonic, also known as a memory aid, a tool that helps you remember an idea or phrase with a pattern of letters, numbers, or relatable associations (Ornstein et al., 2013)." Some of the references that FN uses to enrich vocabulary are by effectively using online media such as YouTube, podcasts, movies, and songs; this is to improve the pronunciation of words and Practice listening. The advantage of learning from song and movie lyrics is finding words used in everyday life, then continuing with regular Practice on listening and speaking skills, namely applying new vocabulary in the context of conversation, both with yourself and others. He does this to be younger and to remember vocabulary. In addition to Mnemonic, FN also uses vocabulary mastery techniques by focusing on conjugation techniques. Conjugation in linguistic terms is a system of verb change forms related to the number, gender, mode, and time (found in flexion language), or in Arabic terms; it is Tasrif the focus on conjugation is also a practical technique to enrich vocabulary by knowing word derivation. Regarding the Mnemonic technique as an FN learning technique, researchers have not analyzed whether FN uses this technique in its entirety, modification, or development.

Learning Arabic as a foreign language is an integral part of all developments that occur in the world of foreign language education, especially in an era where digital technology has united the world community in communicating and has changed many ways of seeing and has become a new world that is different from the current era. Previous. Therefore, this research requires further research regarding applying FN learning concepts and methods in the Arabic language learning process in formal educational institutions.

CONCLUSION

Fiki Naki is one of the phenomena of self-taught foreign language learners who intensify the use of online media to learn. The FN learning model is compatible with today's digital age. The characteristics that learners must have in this digital age include having a high level of learning autonomy, the ability to use online media effectively as a learning medium, Net-Centric or digital native. The FN learning model can be adapted to foreign language learning in schools and colleges to use foreign languages in simple conversations with native speakers of the target language, not for academic purposes. The concept of learning FN consists of two: psychic and non-psychic. FN's psychic learning concepts include Learning by fun, high determination and consistency, confidence in using language, and independence in learning. The concepts of non-psychic learning include Self-taught, intensive learning, direct language practice, both imaginary with oneself and with native speakers of the target language, mastery of vocabulary and phrases with keyword strategies, and effective use of online media. At the same time, the learning method that FN uses is a communicative method with several learning techniques, including a focus on listening and speaking skills, using Mnemonic techniques in vocabulary mastery, and conjugation mastery techniques.

The Fiki Naki overview explores alternative concepts and methods for Arabic learning in the digital age, emphasizing the need to adapt language education to the dynamic nature of technology. Educators and learners can enhance Arabic language instruction by leveraging innovative tools and resources. The digital age provides interactive platforms, immersive experiences, and personalized learning paths, transforming traditional language acquisition. These efforts address challenges in conventional teaching, catering to diverse global learning preferences. Fiki Naki's exploration signifies a commitment to an inclusive environment for Arabic language learners worldwide. Collaboration among educators, learners, and technology developers is crucial in shaping the future of language education. Integrating linguistic expertise with technology can revolutionize language learning, bridging gaps and promoting cultural understanding. Fiki Naki's overview highlights the importance of evolving language education strategies for a dynamic and accessible approach to teaching Arabic in the digital age. This research needs to be continued in other research to implement the concepts and methods of foreign Language learning in this digital age in formal education at the secondary school and college levels. We thank the Directorate of Research and Community Service of Universitas Islam Riau for funding this research.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

They were studying conception and design: Samin, SM. Author; data collection: Samin, SM. Author, Dakhilullah, TMD. Sanjaya, M. Author; analysis and interpretation of results: Samin, SM. Author; manuscript draft preparation: Samin, SM. Author. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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